

Simplified centroiding algorithm for radiation test data

L. Lindegren

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ABSTRACT. A simple algorithm is proposed for estimating the centroid position, flux, background and background gradient from an extended window (at least 10 samples). The algorithm could be applied to the data sets generated by the CCD radiation tests to investigate the possible bias effects introduced by background gradients. A Fortran implementation is provided.

1 Introduction

CTI effects in irradiated CCDs generally cause a backward centroid shift due to the delayed release of trapped charges. However, analysis of the on-going CCD radiation tests using charge injection has shown that there is sometimes a shift in the opposite direction, so that the image centroid appears to be *advanced* rather than delayed. It has been suggested that this could be caused by a gradient in the background level resulting from the declining release of charges that were trapped in a previous charge injection and/or star transit. The simultaneous presence of positional biases working in opposite directions complicates the physical modelling of the total bias and it would clearly be an advantage if they could be at least partially separated in the analysis.

If background gradients are indeed the cause of the observed negative bias, an obvious remedy could be to estimate the background and its gradient simultaneously with the centroiding. In the standard operational AF window, having an AL width of only 6 samples, this is probably very difficult to achieve. However, in the test data we may use samples further away from the centroid to determine the background in a reliable way. The present algorithm is based on the assumption that there are enough samples to allow an independent estimation of the local background and gradient. A window of at least $n = 10$ samples (but more likely $n = 15$ to 20 samples) will be needed, with the star image well centred in the window.

2 Background estimation and correction

The proposed algorithm is extremely simple: Assume that, out of the n samples in the window, the outermost n_b samples at each end are little affected by the LSF. Then the mean values of the first and last n_b samples provides two estimates of the background from which a linearly varying background can be estimated (Fig. 1).

FIGURE 1: Illustrating the estimation of a linearly varying background in the case when $n = 15$ and $n_b = 2$. The filled circles are the n data points (counts c_i), the crosses at A and B are the background estimates obtained as the mean values of the first and last n_b data points, and the solid line is the estimated background. The dashed vertical lines show the centroid position (ξ , middle line) derived with scale parameter $s = 2.9$, and the support $[\xi - s, \xi + s]$ of the corresponding weighting function.

Let x be the position coordinate expressed in samples, so that $x = 1$ for the first sample (c_1), up to $x = n$ for the last (c_n). Introduce the reference position $x_{\text{ref}} = (1 + n)/2$ and define the background model as

$$b(x) = b + (x - x_{\text{ref}})g \quad (1)$$

with parameters $b = (\text{background at } x_{\text{ref}})$, and $g = (\text{background gradient})$. These parameters are then estimated as

$$b_{\text{est}} = (c_A + c_B)/2, \quad g_{\text{est}} = (c_B - c_A)/(n - n_b) \quad (2)$$

where

$$c_A = \frac{1}{n_b} \sum_{k=1}^{n_b} c_k, \quad c_B = \frac{1}{n_b} \sum_{k=1}^{n_b} c_{n+1-k}, \quad (3)$$

The background-corrected counts are

$$d_i = c_i - b_{\text{est}} - (i - x_{\text{ref}})g_{\text{est}}, \quad i = 1 \dots n \quad (4)$$

The flux and centroid estimation should now use $\{d_i\}$ instead of $\{c_i\}$. In principle, the same algorithms as before could be used (e.g., `locest`), but in the following we consider an alternative, much simpler method.

3 Flux estimation

The flux is estimated as the sum of the corrected counts,

$$f_{\text{est}} = \sum_{k=1}^n d_i \quad (5)$$

Note that the sum could just as well have been taken over $k = n_b + 1$ to $n - n_b$, since the outermost $2n_b$ samples give no net contribution with to the adopted background estimate.

4 Centroid estimation

A conventional definition of the ‘centroid’ for an asymmetric LSF was proposed in [2], based on Tukey’s biweight (TBW) [3], a weighting function with a limited support depending on the scale parameter s . It was also noted (Sect. 4 of [2]) that a discrete version of TBW method could be used for centroiding on real data samples without first having to calibrate the LSF. This method will not be as accurate as a full Maximum Likelihood estimation of the centroid, e.g. by the `locest` algorithm [1], but the relative loss of accuracy (less than a factor 2) may be well motivated by the simplicity of the approach in certain applications such as the analysis of the radiation test data and the IDT. In order to use the TBW centroiding algorithm on real AF data with only 6 samples per window, it is essential that the scale parameter s does not exceed 3. In [2] it was concluded that $s = 2.7$ is optimal for the particular LSFs considered. Later studies have concluded that a slightly larger value is advantageous, e.g. $s = 2.9$ (assumed below).

Following [2], Eq. (17), the centroid position ξ of the corrected samples $\{d_i\}$ is obtained by solving the equation

$$\sum_{k=1}^n d_k w\left(\frac{k - \xi}{s}\right) = 0 \quad (6)$$

where

$$w(z) = \begin{cases} z(1 - z^2)^2 & \text{if } |z| < 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

for given scale parameter s . The equation is quickly solved by Newton–Raphson iteration as described in [2], provided a reasonable starting approximation is available for ξ . Usually the highest value among the n samples can be taken as the starting approximation.

References

- [1] Lindegren L., 2000: *Centroiding on GAIA CCD sample data*, SAG–LL–032 (4 October 2000)
- [2] Lindegren L., 2006: *Centroid definition for the Astro Line Spread Function*, GAIA–C2–TN–LU–LL–068-1 (11 July 2006)
- [3] Press W.H., Flannery B.P., Teukolsky S.A., Vetterling W.T., 1992: *Numerical recipes in Fortran*, Cambridge University Press (free on-line version available at <http://www.nr.com/>)

Acronyms

The following table has been generated from the on-line Gaia acronym list:

Acronym	Description
AF	Astrometric Field (in Astro)
AL	ALong scan (direction)
CCD	Charge-Coupled Device
CTI	Charge Transfer Inefficiency
LSF	Line-Spread Function
TBW	Tukey's biweight
WG	Working Group

Appendix: Fortran implementation

The following is a Fortran implementation of the algorithm described above. It takes a REAL array `c(1:n)` of counts as input, and returns estimates of the centroid ($\xi = \mathbf{x}_{\text{est}}$), flux ($f_{\text{est}} = \mathbf{fest}$), background at x_{ref} ($b_{\text{est}} = \mathbf{best}$) and background gradient ($g_{\text{est}} = \mathbf{gest}$). The logical input argument `ifgrad` is a switch for the gradient estimator; `ifgrad = .FALSE.` imposes a zero gradient.

The code (in file `cent.f`) is provided with a main program (in file `testcent.f`) that performs a simple test of the algorithm.

File: cent.f

```
*****
      SUBROUTINE cent(n, nb, c, s, ifgrad,
+                xest, fest, best, gest, ierr)
*****
c
c GAIA - Calibration WG - Centroid estimation on sloping background
c
c L. Lindegren 2007 Feb 22
c
c This subroutine takes a (double-precision) array c(1:n) (n .GE. 10)
c of CCD samples, with a peak somewhere near the centre, and returns
c the estimated centroid position, total flux in the peak, background
c level and (optionally) background gradient. The centroid is the
c Tukey's biweight for given parameter s (s = 2.7-3.0 is recommended).
c
c INPUT:
c   n       = (INTEGER) number of samples, must be at least 10
c   nb      = (INTEGER) number of samples (at each end) used for
c             background and gradient estimation, must be >0 and <n/2
c   c()     = (REAL*8) array of n samples
c   s       = (REAL*8) scale parameter for Tukey's biweight (note 1)
c   ifgrad  = (LOGICAL) .TRUE. if background gradient should be
c             estimated (otherwise, the gradient is forced to 0)
c
c OUTPUT:
c   xest    = (REAL*8) estimated centroid position (note 2)
c   fest    = (REAL*8) estimated flux (note 2)
c   best    = (REAL*8) estimated background at xref (note 4)
c   gest    = (REAL*8) estimated background gradient (per sample),
c             or 0 if ifgrad = .FALSE. (note 5)
c   ierr    = (INTEGER) 0 for successful centroiding, otherwise > 0
c             (see SUBROUTINE tukeybw() for error conditions)
c
c NOTES:
c
c 1. According to Ref. 1, the recommended value for s is 2.7.
c    However, in general s could be optimised for precision, e.g.
c    a somewhat larger value may be preferred if the LSF is wider
c    than assumed in Ref. 1. Test with a gaussian LSF of standard
c    width 0.9-1 sample suggests that s = 2.9 is the best choice.
c
c 2. The centroid position (xest) is expressed in samples on a scale
c    where x = 1 at the centre of the first sample, etc.
c
c 3. The flux is the sum of the counts minus the background.
c
c 4. xref = (1+n)/2 is the mid-point of the array. When a gradient
c    is estimated, the background value best refers to this point
c    [so the estimated background at point x is best + gest*(x-xref)].
c
c 5. When ifgrad = .FALSE. the centroiding is done under the
c    assumption that there is no background gradient, and gest = 0
c    is returned.
c
c REFERENCES:
c   1. GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-068-1 (centroiding and Tukey's biweight)
c   2. GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-069-1 (centroiding on a gradient background)
c
      IMPLICIT REAL*8 (a-h,o-z)
```

```

PARAMETER (nmax = 100)
DIMENSION c(n), d(nmax)
LOGICAL ifgrad
c
IF (n .LT. 10) STOP 'n must be at least 10'
IF (n .GT. nmax) STOP 'n > nmax, please increase nmax!'
IF (nb .LT. 1) STOP 'nb must be at least 1'
IF (nb .GT. n/2) STOP 'nb must be less than n/2'
xref = dble(1+n)/2d0
c
c Estimate the background at each end of the window (point A and B):
c
      bA = 0d0
      bB = 0d0
      DO k = 1, nb
         bA = bA + c(k)
         bB = bB + c(n+1-k)
      ENDDO
      bA = bA/dble(nb)
      bB = bB/dble(nb)
c
c Hence the background at xref (best) and gradient (gest):
c
      IF (ifgrad) THEN
         best = (bA + bB)/2d0
         gest = (bB - bA)/dble(n-nb)
      ELSE
         best = (bA + bB)/2d0
         gest = 0d0
      ENDIF
c
c Correct the counts for the background and estimate flux:
c
      fest = 0d0
      DO k = 1, n
         x = dble(k)
         b = best + gest*(x - xref)
         d(k) = c(k) - b
         fest = fest + d(k)
      ENDDO
c
c Do centroiding on d(1:n) using Tukey's biweight:
c
      CALL tukeybw(n, d, s,      xest, ierr)
c
      RETURN
      END
c*****
      SUBROUTINE tukeybw(n, c, s,      xest, ierr)
c*****
c
c GAIA - CU3 - Centroid estimation using Tukey's biweight
c
c L. Lindegren 2007 Feb 22
c
c This subroutine takes a (double-precision) array c(1:n) (n .GE. 6)
c of CCD samples, with a peak somewhere near the centre, and returns
c the estimated centroid position, using Tukey's biweight with scale
c parameter s (s = 2.7 is recommended).
c
c INPUT:
c   n      = (INTEGER) number of samples, must be at least 6

```

```

c   c()      = (REAL*8) array of n samples
c   s       = (REAL*8) scale parameter for Tukey's biweight
c
c   OUTPUT:
c   xest    = (REAL*8) estimated centroid position (note 1)
c   ierr    = 0 if estimation is OK
c           = 1 if estimation was made but result is doubtful (note 2)
c           = 2 if estimation failed (note 3)
c
c   NOTES:
c
c   1. The centroid position (xest) is expressed in samples on a scale
c      where x = 1 at the centre of the first sample, etc.
c
c   2. The estimation is doubtful (ierr = 1) if the support of
c       $w((k-xest)/s)$  is not entirely within the window (i.e., if
c       $xest-s < 1$  or  $xest+s > n$ )
c
c   3. Failure (ierr = 2) occurs if  $n < 6$ , if Eq. (17) in Ref. 1 has
c      no solution corresponding to a (positive) peak within the given
c      window (positive peak means  $2*c(k)-c(k-1)-c(k+1) > 0$  for some k),
c      if Eq. (18) does not converge in maxiter iterations, or if the
c      converged value is outside the window.
c
c   REFERENCE:
c   1. GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-068-1
c
c      IMPLICIT REAL*8 (a-h,o-z)
c      PARAMETER (nmin = 6, maxiter = 10, tolerance = 1d-6)
c      DIMENSION c(n)
c
c      IF (n .LT. nmin) THEN
c         ierr = 2
c         RETURN
c      ENDIF
c
c   Locate the highest value in the range 2 to n-1:
c
c      cmax = -1d300
c      kmax = 0
c      DO k = 2, n-1
c         IF (c(k) .GT. cmax) THEN
c            cmax = c(k)
c            kmax = k
c         ENDIF
c      ENDDO
c      IF (kmax .LT. 1) THEN
c         ierr = 2
c         RETURN
c      ENDIF
c
c   Check that it is a positive peak:
c
c      peak = 2d0 * c(kmax) - c(kmax-1) - c(kmax+1)
c      IF (peak .LE. 0d0) THEN
c         ierr = 2
c         RETURN
c      ENDIF
c
c   Use kmax as starting value for xest and improve by
c   Newton-Raphson iteration using Eq. (18) in Ref. 1:
c

```

```

xest = dble(kmax)
DO iter = 1, maxiter
  CALL sums(n, c, s, xest, q0, q1)
  dx = s*q0/q1
  IF (dabs(dx) .GT. 1d0) THEN
    dx = dsign(1d0, dx)
  ENDIF
  xest = xest + dx
  IF (dabs(dx) .LT. tolerance) GOTO 100
ENDDO
ierr = 2
RETURN
c
100 CONTINUE
c
c Iteration converged; check validity of result:
c
  ierr = 0
  IF (xest .LT. 1d0 .OR. xest .GT. dble(n)) THEN
    ierr = 2
    RETURN
  ELSEIF (xest-s .LT. 1d0 .OR. xest+s .GT. dble(n)) THEN
    ierr = 1
    RETURN
  ENDIF
c
c All OK:
c
  ierr = 0
  RETURN
END
c*****
SUBROUTINE sums(n, c, s, x, sum0, sum1)
c*****
c
c Calculates the sums in Eq. (18) for given c(1:n), s and x
c (sum0 = upper sum, sum1 = lower sum)
c
  IMPLICIT REAL*8 (a-h,o-z)
  DIMENSION c(n)
  k1 = max0(1, nint(x-s+0.49d0))
  k2 = min0(n, nint(x+s-0.49d0))
  sum0 = 0d0
  sum1 = 0d0
  DO k = k1, k2
    z = (dble(k) - x)/s
    CALL wtukey(z, w, w1)
    sum0 = sum0 + c(k) * w
    sum1 = sum1 + c(k) * w1
  ENDDO
  RETURN
END
c*****
SUBROUTINE wtukey(z, w, w1)
c*****
c
c GAIA - CU3 - Centroid estimation using Tukey's biweight - w(z)
c
c L. Lindegren 2007 Feb 22
c
c Calculates the functions w(z) [Eq. (10) in Ref. 1] and w'(z)
c [Eq. (19) in Ref. 1]

```

```
c
c REFERENCE:
c 1. GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-068-1
c
  IMPLICIT REAL*8 (a-h,o-z)
  zabs = dabs(z)
  IF (zabs .LT. 1d0) THEN
    z2 = z*z
    w = z*(1d0 - z2)**2
    w1 = (1d0 - 5d0*z2) * (1d0 - z2)
  ELSE
    w = 0d0
    w1 = 0d0
  ENDIF
  RETURN
  END
```

File: testcent.f

```
PROGRAM testcent
c Main program for calling and testing SUBROUTINE cent.
c Running this should print 'test OK' on standard output.
c L Lindegren, 2007 Feb 22
  IMPLICIT REAL*8 (a-h,o-z)
  PARAMETER (nmax = 15)
  REAL*8 c(nmax)
  LOGICAL ifgrad
c
  DATA c / 404.8d0, 400.1d0, 396.9d0, 406.0d0, 436.5d0,
+          724.6d0, 2239.9d0, 3597.0d0, 2005.3d0, 764.2d0,
+          450.2d0, 354.6d0, 311.7d0, 295.3d0, 280.3d0 /
  n = 15
  nb = 2
  s = 2.9d0
  ifailsum = 0
c
  ifgrad = .TRUE.
  CALL cent(n, nb, c, s, ifgrad, xest, fest, best, gest, ierr)
  IF (ierr .NE. 0) THEN
    PRINT *, 'cent failed for ifgrad = ',ifgrad,' with ierr =',ierr
    ifailsum = ifailsum + 1
  ENDIF
  ifailsum = ifailsum + ifail(1, xest, 7.967760884403848d0, 1d-12)
  ifailsum = ifailsum + ifail(2, fest, 7890.5250000000001d0, 1d-10)
  ifailsum = ifailsum + ifail(3, best, 345.12500000000000d0, 1d-11)
  ifailsum = ifailsum + ifail(4, gest, -8.819230769230773d0, 1d-12)
c
  ifgrad = .FALSE.
  CALL cent(n, nb, c, s, ifgrad, xest, fest, best, gest, ierr)
  IF (ierr .NE. 0) THEN
    PRINT *, 'cent failed for ifgrad = ',ifgrad,' with ierr =',ierr
    ifailsum = ifailsum + 1
  ENDIF
  ifailsum = ifailsum + ifail(5, xest, 7.959388923589598d0, 1d-12)
  ifailsum = ifailsum + ifail(6, fest, 7890.5250000000001d0, 1d-10)
  ifailsum = ifailsum + ifail(7, best, 345.12500000000000d0, 1d-11)
  ifailsum = ifailsum + ifail(8, gest, 0.000000000000000d0, 1d-12)
c
  IF (ifailsum .EQ. 0) THEN
    PRINT *, 'test OK'
  ELSE
    PRINT *, 'test failed'
  ENDIF
END
c*****
INTEGER FUNCTION ifail(icase, val1, val2, tol)
c*****
  INTEGER icase
  REAL*8 val1, val2, tol
  IF (dabs(val1-val2) .GT. tol) THEN
    PRINT *, 'failure in case ',icase
    PRINT *, 'values compared = ', val1, val2
    ifail = 1
  ELSE
    ifail = 0
  ENDIF
  RETURN
END
```